

($K_b = 4.2 \times 10^{-10}$) both *m*-chloro ($K_b = 0.3 \times 10^{-10}$) and *p*-chloro ($K_b = 1.5 \times 10^{-10}$) anilines are less basic. However, *p*-chloroaniline is significantly more basic of the two. Hence the exclusive formation of I (R = Cl) involving the more basic para amino group is understandable.

In contrast to chloroanilines, both *m*-toluidine ($K_b = 4.9 \times 10^{-10}$) and *p*-toluidine ($K_b = 12 \times 10^{-10}$) are more basic compared to aniline. Thus the formation of both I and II (R = CH₃) the former in larger proportion, from 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine and acetylacetone can readily be understood.

Since both *m*-nitro ($K_b = 0.032 \times 10^{-10}$) and *p*-nitro ($K_b = 0.001 \times 10^{-10}$) anilines are far less basic than aniline, the inability of 4-nitro-*o*-phenylenediamine to react with acetylacetone appears reasonable.

Experimental

1. *Condensation of 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine with acetylacetone*: To a solution of 4-chloro-*o*-phenylenediamine (14.2 g, 100 m Mol) in acetic acid (100 ml) was added a similar solution of acetylacetone (12 g, 100 m Mol) at room temp. The mixture was stirred for 1 hr and diluted with cold water. The aqueous acid solution was made ammoniacal and extracted with chloroform. The dried chloroform extract after removal of the solvent was distilled under reduced pressure. *N*-(2-amino-4-chlorophenyl)-2,5-dimethyl pyrrole (11.2 g, 55%) b.p. 142°/2.5 mm. was obtained as a light brown solid which on passing through a column of alumina using petroleum ether as solvent yielded a colourless sample, m.p. 92°-3°. ν_{max} (3580 cm⁻¹, 3700 cm⁻¹ for -NH₂), NMR: δ 1.97 (6H, -CH₃); 3.42 (2H, -NH₂); 5.89 (2H, H in 2 and 3 of pyrrole) and 7.00 (3H, phenyl). Found: 12.92; C₁₂H₁₃ClN₂ requires N: 12.7%.

2. *Condensation of 4-methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine with acetylacetone*: 4-Methyl-*o*-phenylenediamine (12.2 g, 100 m Mol) was allowed to react with acetylacetone in the same way as above. The amino compound (13 g, 65%) was obtained on distillation at 122°-3°/1 mm. ν_{max} (3580 cm⁻¹ and 3720 cm⁻¹ for -NH₂), NMR: δ 1.92 (6H, -CH₃ in the pyrrole ring); 2.35 (3H, -CH₃ of the aromatic ring); 3.25 (2H, -NH₂), 5.77 (2H, H in 2 and 3 of pyrrole) and 6.66 (CH, phenyl ring). Found 13.92; C₁₃H₁₆N₂ requires N: 14.0%.

The compound was subjected to GLC (oven temp. 160°, main oven temp. 320° and injection temp. 310°) using apiezone column (30 m) when two peaks with retention times of 22.2 min. (60%) and 19.5 min. (40%) were observed. The former peak corresponded to I (R = CH₃).

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Kinetic Studies on the Coagulation Process of Ferric Arsenate Sol at Different Stages of Dialysis

KRISHNA RAINA & K. L. HANDOO

Chemistry Department, University of Saugor, Sagar (M.P.)

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A NUMBER of papers¹⁻¹⁰ have appeared on the tyndallometric and extinction techniques that have been employed for following the coagulation process of a host of sols. The aforesaid techniques were used to investigate the process of coagulation of ferric arsenate sol by electrolyte amounts $\ll C_c$ (Coagulation Concentration) and far above this value at different stages of dialysis of the sol, and the record of Extinction-time curves is given in the present communication.

Experimental

Ferric arsenate sol was prepared and kept for dialysis in the same manner as described elsewhere¹¹. During the span of dialysis, three samples were withdrawn each representing a particular form of purity. The purity of the sol was assessed by viewing the reciprocal coagulation concentration of K₂SO₄ for each form of the sol (vide table 1) and the composition was determined in terms of Fe₂O₃, AsO₄³⁻, Cl- contents in gms/lit. The sols were coagulated with K₂SO₄ and the process of coagulation was studied by obtaining the plots of extinction (absorbance) *versus* time for different electrolyte concentrations lying in the vicinity of coagulation concentration and also in the range required for bringing about rapid coagulation. Use was made of Spekol Spectro-colorimeter set at 500 nm and the changes in extinction with the progress of time were recorded after mixing 10 ml of a particular electrolyte solution with 10 ml of the sol maintaining the same experimental conditions throughout the determination.

Discussion

Figs. 1 & 2 indicate that the sols show an auto-catalytic behaviour when coagulated with electrolyte concentrations $\ll C_c$. According to Verwey and Overbeek¹², who have developed the concept of de Boer¹³ and Hamaker¹⁴, the system behaves as a stable suspension in which the potential energy curves have a maxima \gg KT. Long range attraction is always a consequence of London-Vander Waals forces, but repulsion may originate in a variety of ways. For example, when the sols of not much purity

NOTES

TABLE 1

Days of Dialysis	Amt. in gms/lit of			Coagulation Concentration millimoles, K_2SO_4	Reciprocal coagulation concentration
	Fe_2O_3	ASO_4^{3-}	Cl^-		
1	8.432	7.110	14.250	29.50	0.033
4	7.214	6.080	4.450	4.40	0.227
13	5.390	5.210	2.865	0.28	3.571

are treated with smaller concentrations of the electrolyte, the process of flocculation itself causes marked changes in the distribution of ions between the double layer and the disperse medium with the

It is also seen from figs. 1-2 that for higher concentrations of the electrolyte the autocatalytic nature of the curves disappears and there is, initially with time, a rapid rise in the extinction values indicating thereby a state of rapid coagulation. When, however, still higher concentrations of the electrolyte are taken, there is a flattening of the extinction-time curves with lower extinction maxima indicating as if a decrease in the rate of coagulation has taken place. Here, the coagulation has been so rapid that the flocs formed were loose and irregular which in turn absorbed less light. In well dialyzed sols, addition of even minutely low quantities of electrolyte results in the rapid formation of a large number of coagulating nuclei. In this system, charges of the sol particles are practically completely removed and consequently when coagulation takes place, particles stick where they touch each other without getting rearranged into better contacts. In this way flocs formed have very low density and thus give lower values of extinction maxima (vide Fig. 3). The ease with which the curves remain

Fig. 1. Sol I (Sol dialysed for 1 day)

result that the surface potential of the aggregate is altered and consequently the suspension gets stabilized upto some stage of aggregation. The slowness of the rate in the beginning as shown by the meagre

Fig. 2. Sol II (Sol dialysed for 4 days)

change in extinction values may be ascribe to the aforesaid reason. The increase in the coagulation rate after the induction period as seen by the S-shaped nature of some curves in figs 1-2 has been widely reported and discussed by several workers¹⁵⁻¹⁹ earlier.

Fig. 3. Sol III (Sol dialysed for 13 days)

parallel to time axis, after the maximum extinction is reached, shows that the flocs do not finally settle down, but instead get oriented into a gel structure.

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Halide and Oxidehalide Complexes of Chromium with 2,2'-Bipyridine

MANINDRA N. MAJUMDER & AMIT K. SAHA

Department of Chemistry, University of Kalyani, Kalyani,
West Bengal

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CHROMYL chloride may act as a Lewis acid and form addition compounds with donor molecules. Some examples are known^{1,2}, but other possibilities have not been fully explored, nor the compounds well studied. No complex bromides or iodides have been reported. Complex compounds of chromium in oxidations states other than 2 and 3

are not many³, particularly the oxidehalide complexes in 4, 5 and 6 oxidation states are rare and of low stability.

The present communication gives a preliminary report on some 2,2'-bipyridine complexes of chromium in 6, 4, 3 and 1 oxidation states.

Experimental

Chromyl chloride was prepared by the usual method and 2,2'-bipyridine was of reagent quality. Acetic acid and benzene were purified and dried as usual.

Compounds prepared with their elemental analysis and some physical and chemical properties are given in table 1.

Magnetic moment measurements were made at room temperature (28°) by the guoy method and the corrected values of the magnetic moments were 1.08, 3.28 and 3.35 for (I), (II) and (IV) respectively which is taken to indicate the presence of 0, 2 and 3 unpaired electrons in the *d*-levels of chromium³.

Conductivity measurements at room temperature in purified formamide solutions at different concentrations did not give a straightline plot (Λ vs \sqrt{c}) and Λ_0 value was found to be 58 ohm⁻¹ cm², showing that the compound is an weak electrolyte.

The infra-red spectra of the compounds have been recorded in Nujol mull from 4000 cm⁻¹ to 700 cm⁻¹. None of these compounds exhibit any i.r. peak beyond 2900 cm⁻¹ and hence O-H group is absent. The strong bipyridine peak at 763 cm⁻¹ has shifted to 775 cm⁻¹ and a weak one at 730 cm⁻¹ to 735 cm⁻¹ with increase in intensity on complexation. (I) shows two peaks at 955 cm⁻¹ and 895 cm⁻¹ which are due to Cr-O. A common peak at 980 cm⁻¹ is present in (II) and (III) and they are assigned to Cr-O. (IV) does not contain any peak between 1000 cm⁻¹ and 800 cm⁻¹ which proves the absence of Cr-O group in conformity with chemical evidence.

TABLE I

Compounds	Mode of preparation	Analytical results	General properties
(I) Dioxodichloro-2,2'-bipyridine chromium (VI) CrO ₂ Cl ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	By the interaction of chromyl chloride and bipyridine in acetic acid medium in the cold.	Found : Cr = 16.44%; Cl = 21.40; N = 8.84, Valency = 6.0. Calculated : Cr = 16.70, Cl = 22.80, N = 9.0, valency = 6.0.	Red, Stable, Solid, slowly decompose on storage. Sensitive to light, moisture and heat. Insoluble in water.
(II) Mono-oxo-di-iodo-2,2' bipyridine chromium (IV) CrOI ₂ .C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Reducing (I) with hydroiodic acid solution.	Found : Cr = 10.70, Cl = 52.10, valency = 4.1. Calc.: Cr = 10.87, I = 53.13, valency = 4.0.	Deep violet stable solid, rather inert. Sparingly soluble in water and other common organic solvents.
(III) Mono-oxo-monochloro-2,2'-bipyridine chromium (III) CrOCl.C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂	Isothermal heating of (I) for 4 hours at 200°-280°C in N ₂ -atmosphere.	Found : Cr = 19.77, Cl = 13.80, loss = 15.67. Calc.: Cr = 20.00, Cl = 13.70, loss = 16.56.	Greenish, stable solid.
(IV) Chloro (2,2'-bipyridine) chromium (I) CrCl.C ₁₀ H ₈ N ₂ *	Isothermal heating in dry N ₂ -atmosphere at 370° to constant weight.	Found : Cr = 21.99, Cl = 15.77, valency = 0.95. Calc.: Cr = 21.40, Cl = 14.57, valency = 1.0.	Black solid, insoluble in water and most other common solvents. Rather inert.

* When (IV) is prepared most of the chlorine is evolved as HCl and bipyridine in (IV) appears to be partly oxidised.